

Study of nonlinearity of capital redistribution in economic systems

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Аннотация. Целью настоящего исследования является проверка на цифровых моделях гипотезы незначимости для экономических систем в целом влияния нелинейности перераспределения капиталов при имеющих место в реальности больших ошибках оценивания. Для этого предложено использовать цифровую модель. Расширение областей ее применения доказывает, что эта модель становится все более универсальной. Поэтому необходимо пересмотреть точность используемых в ней обоснований. В модели рынок рассматривается как новая кооперативная сущность. Для продвижения цифровой модели в качестве универсального инструментария требуется снять противоречие нелинейности. Более тонкий анализ предполагает включение в решение основных задач экономики рандомизированных индивидуальных леонтьевских матриц. В ходе проведения опросов обычных людей и профессиональных экономистов было выявлено, что их результаты показывают значительный разброс оценок фундаментальности требования нелинейности перераспределения. В методологическом плане получены эмпирические результаты моделирования воздействия нелинейности доходов на страны с разным уровнем обеспечения капиталом и ресурсами. Для учета огромных случайных колебаний динамики развития экономической системы при больших ошибках оценивания, представляется целесообразным использовать схему конкуренции двух почти тождественных стран, отличающихся по трем факторам: нелинейность перераспределения; уровень случайных ошибок оценивания; обеспеченность природными ресурсами.

Abstract. The objective of this study is to test the hypothesis of insignificance of the impact of capital redistribution nonlinearity on economic systems as a whole using digital models given large estimation errors that occur in reality. For this purpose, it is proposed to use a digital model. The expansion of its application areas proves that this model is becoming increasingly universal. Therefore, it is necessary to reconsider the justifications used in it. The model regards the market as a new cooperative entity. To promote the digital model as a universal tool, it is necessary to remove the contradiction of nonlinearity. A more subtle analysis involves including randomized individual Leontief matrices in solving the main problems of the economy. In the course of surveys of ordinary people and professional economists, it was revealed that their results show a significant spread in estimates of the fundamentality of the requirement for redistribution nonlinearity. In methodological terms, empirical results were obtained by modeling the impact of income nonlinearity on countries with different levels of capital and resource endowment. To take into account huge random fluctuations in the dynamics of economic system development given large estimation errors, it seems advisable to use a competition scheme of two almost identical countries that differ in three factors: redistribution nonlinearity; level of random estimation errors; availability of natural resources.

Ключевые слова: экономические системы, цифровые модели, рыночные и гибридные экономики, нелинейность перераспределения капиталов, ошибки оценивания.

Keywords: economic systems, digital models, market and hybrid economies, nonlinearity of capital redistribution, estimation errors.

Introduction

In a series of previous works, the authors used a digital model of market and hybrid economies

[1] to solve a number of practical and theoretical economic problems, from optimizing the allocation of resources for the production of agricultural crops ([2],

[3]) to assessing the negative effects of marginal transformation in the electric power industry ([4], [5], [6]). The expansion of the model's scope makes it increasingly universal. This forces us to reconsider the accuracy of its justifications.

Purpose of the study

The aim of this study is to test, using digital models, the hypothesis of the insignificance for economic systems as a whole of the impact of nonlinearity in the redistribution of capital given the large estimation errors that occur in reality.

Methods and materials

The basic principles of the model are simple and logical. We consider the market not as a mechanical sum of agents interacting in exchange transactions, but as a cooperative new entity that automatically solves two main tasks of the economy:

1. Determination (assessment) of market values.
2. Redistribution of capital based on the results of exchange from inefficient agents (assessors) to efficient ones.

The second statement in the language of stock markets is formulated as "work (evaluate) worse than the market - you lose money, evaluate better - you get." In the most general formulation - "we are all evaluators in this world, and the change in our state depends on individual evaluation errors." However, the model can also be formulated in the usual terms of the relationship between the market price and the cost of goods.

At the same time, taking into account large errors by metrology standards (for example, the cost of "grain" produced by agents has a huge random component), both systematic and random, we initially considered it appropriate to model axioms (1) and (2) in a linear approximation.

Then, for a single-commodity model without taking into account natural resources, they are reduced to the simplest formula for the change in capital A over a cycle $i = i+1$, namely:

$$A(i+1) = A(i) + A(i) \cdot \langle x(i) \rangle - A(i) \cdot x(i) \quad (1)$$

where i – cycle;

$A(i)$ – vector of capitals of agents involved in exchange transactions on the i -cycle;

$x(i)$ – vector of relative individual deviations of production costs of the "goods" (more broadly relative errors of estimation) of agents from the market value;

\cdot – symbol for element-wise matrix multiplication.

$\langle x(i) \rangle$ – market value assessment. It is defined as the most probable price, and is practically found by linear capitalistic averaging [7].

$$\langle x(i) \rangle = (At(i) \cdot x(i)) \cdot (At(i) \cdot 1)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

In this case, the second formula implements the first axiom in a linear approximation, and the first formula implements the second axiom also in a linear approximation. The obligatory use of natural resources, in particular labor, which, in fact, provide growth in i , is most easily modeled by an additional agent with an available quantity of A and a conditional cost price (μ) equal to the cost price of the 0-agent, i.e. a non-profitable and break-even agent at a given level of availability of natural resources P .

This is expressed by the formula (3):

$$Q(i) = At(i) \cdot 1 \quad (3)$$

where Q – total capital of the system;

1 – unit vector.

An approximate transition to a multi-commodity (multi-industry) model comes down to constructing a block vector A , which we, in particular, used in the analysis of marginal pricing in multi-industry agriculture and electric power engineering [2], [3], [4], [5], [6].

A more subtle analysis involves including randomized individual Leontief matrices in expressions (1) and (2) [7]. However, in order to promote the model as universal, it is desirable to remove the nonlinearity contradiction.

There are serious studies, in particular, by Nobel laureates Kahneman and others [8], who, using real passive and active experiments, prove that in formula (1), redistribution is nonlinear.

Also, no less serious researchers, in particular Maslov [9], argue that averaging according to formula (2) should also be nonlinear.

In this paper, we will not test the nonlinearity of averaging, primarily because we do not know of a single practical appraiser who "legally" applies nonlinear averaging in assessing market value.

According to formula (1), the picture is not so obvious. Thus, a survey of ordinary people and professional economists conducted by the authors in August 2022 showed a significant spread in estimates of the fundamentality of the requirement for nonlinearity of redistribution [10].

The hypothesis that needs to be tested on digital models can be formulated as follows.

The impact of nonlinearity of capital redistribution with large estimation errors that occur in reality is not significant for economic systems as a whole.

Realizing the scale of the nonlinearity problem, for the first digital experiments we set ourselves the very modest task of comparing the impact of nonlinearity of redistribution with the impact of experimentally observed errors in estimating market values by agents.

In methodological terms, given the huge random fluctuations in the dynamics of the development

of the modeled economic system with large estimation errors, we considered it appropriate to use a competition scheme for two almost identical countries that differ in three factors:

- 1) nonlinearity of redistribution;
- 2) the level of random estimation errors;
- 3) endowment with natural resources.

Considering that this is primary digital modeling in the logic of planning experiments, we performed numerical experiments at 8 extreme points of the domain of definition for three factors.

In terms of nonlinearity, the reference country has a linear distribution according to (1), while the "experimental" country has a linear distribution according to losses (negative income) and a normalized cubic nonlinear distribution according to income.

In order to imagine the level of impact on a system with triple nonlinearity, we note the following. Let us assume that in a hypothetical system of two groups of agents, the first in the linear version after exchange transactions received 10% of the income, and the second - 90% of the income. Then in the model with triple nonlinearity with renormalization, the first group will receive approximately 0.1% of the income, and the second - approximately 99.9% of the income. This means that our simplified model almost certainly has a stronger impact on the "nonlinearity" parameter on the economic system compared to the actually observed models.

By relatively random errors in estimating agents from 0.1 to 1.0, which, taking into account the

real fluctuations in estimates of market prices of gas and electricity in a number of countries in recent years, seems quite appropriate. Thus, in terms of energy equivalent, given the current OPEC+ stabilized oil prices, gas, taking into account its environmental superiority, should cost around \$1,000 per 1,000 cubic meters [11], [12]. In practice, according to the TTF benchmark, we observed fluctuations of around $\pm \$1,000$ [13]. Incidentally, the market value of gas on a fixed day is determined as the linear weighted average price for spot transactions on that day [14]. This once again confirms the validity of formula (2).

To analyze the provision of conditional countries with accessible natural resources, we will vary the income parameter from one GDP, which corresponds to the level of poorly provided countries, to 10 GDP, which approximately corresponds to countries comparable to Russia. Otherwise, we will model two identical countries with an equal number of agents, the efficiency of which in terms of systematic estimation errors varies from 0.01 to 0.10.

Figures 1-8 show typical results of numerical experiments.

Figures 1 and 2 show the modeling of the impact of income nonlinearity on resource-poor countries with large errors in estimating market values, which is the majority of countries in the world today.

Based on the results of 100 numerical experiments, no significant impact of nonlinearity was found.

Fig. 1. Economic growth of resource-poor countries with large estimation errors with linear income (Upper line – benchmark; Lower line – experimental).

Fig. 2. Economic growth of countries with large estimation errors with income in a triple nonlinear system (Upper line – benchmark; Lower line – experimental).

Figures 3 and 4 simulate the impact of income nonlinearity on resource-poor countries with small market value errors, a rare exception today.

There is a significant acceleration of progress with nonlinear redistribution. However, its level is significantly less than the dependence on estimation

errors and can be considered significant in exceptional cases.

Figures 5 and 6 simulate the impact of nonlinearity on countries with large resources and large estimation errors.

Fig. 3. Economic growth of resource-poor countries with small estimation errors with income in a triple nonlinear system (Upper line – experimental; Lower line – benchmark).

Fig. 4. Economic growth of resource-poor countries with small estimation errors with linear income (Upper line – benchmark; Lower line – experimental).

Fig. 5. Economic growth of resource-rich countries with large estimation errors with income in a triple nonlinear system (Reference line – moderate growth; Experimental line – accelerated growth).

In 100 numerical experiments, there was a wide range of results. In 10-20% of experiments, income nonlinearity accelerates progress. In 30-60% of experiments, a catastrophe of the type shown in Figure 5 occurs. Overall, the experiments do not indicate

a significant effect of nonlinearity on growth dynamics.

The graphs in Figures 7 and 8 show that there is a clear impact of income nonlinearity on progress for countries with large resources and small estimation errors.

Fig. 6. Economic growth of resource-rich countries with large estimation errors with linear income (Benchmark line – normal growth; Experimental line – accelerated growth).

Fig. 7. Economic growth of resource-rich countries with small estimation errors with income in a triple nonlinear system (Upper line – experimental; Lower line – benchmark).

Conclusion

Based on the totality of experiments, we can quite definitely state that the influence of even such a powerful nonlinearity of income redistribution on the dynamics of progress is an order of magnitude weaker than the influence of large random estimation errors and, especially, the influence of the availability of available natural resources.

However, one should take into account the significant difference in the influence of nonlinearity of redistribution on the dynamics of economic growth for countries poorly and strongly endowed with resources with large estimation errors.

Thus, for countries poorly endowed with resources with large estimation errors and nonlinear redistribution of income, economic catastrophe occurs in approximately 90% of numerical experiments.

Fig. 8. Economic growth of resource-rich countries with small estimation errors with linear income (the reference and experimental lines almost coincide, while accelerated growth is observed).

At the same time, for countries strongly endowed with resources with large estimation errors, nonlinear redistribution leads to economic catastrophes in approximately 30% of numerical experiments.

This difference certainly requires more detailed digital modeling, which does not cancel out the main preliminary conclusion about the advisability of using the simplest linear model according to (1) – (3), taking into account the actually observed level of errors in estimating market values in the modern turbulent world.

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